

Jessica Dello Russo

Modern Graffiti in the Jewish Catacombs of the Vigna Randanini in Rome

Questions and comments from those fortunate or persistent enough to gain access to the Jewish catacombs of Rome often draw our attention to elements not really explained in any formal study of these sites. Case in point is a certain Andrea, creator of the Rome-based blog “Dice che a Roma...” describing a recent “avventura casareccia” in the Vigna Randanini catacombs in an entry dated November 1st: http://diceche.blogspot.com/2012_11_01_archive.html. Well-versed in his self-appointed role as a home-grown “Indiana Jones,” Andrea is both fascinated and repulsed by the humid atmosphere, tribes of “cricket spiders” (ragni grillo) dropping down from overhead, and the semi-obstructed galleries leading deeper and deeper into darkness and the unknown.

In the eyes of today’s Romans, however, what is old is in constant contact with the new. We therefore find Andrea taking in not only the ancient epitaphs, wall paintings, and other artifacts still in the site, but also the conspicuous presence of modern graffiti on many of the walls and inscriptions. Andrea is initially appalled by what he regards as signs of vandalism not so different from those generated by the “writer metropolitani” of today, but soon realizes that the damage is, at the very least, close to a century old, and had been carried out while the concept of cultural heritage preservation was still not very well respected or understood – rather an open question, in terms of how much progress has actually been made since that time.

While Andrea dates these graffiti to the 1930’s, their chronology would appear to be more extensive, spanning half a century or more, from the mid-1890’s to the early 1950’s (one of the latest, the signature of PCAS *fossore* Angelo Fiorenza on the reverse of an

inscription near the “Palm Tree” cubiculum, is dated 1948). A nearly illegible scrawl in the “Double Cubiculum” could read “1832”, but that would suggest that that area was already known before its “official” discovery thirty years later, on May 18th, 1862.

As Andrea notes, leaving one’s signature, the date of the visit, and

even one’s place of origin in a funerary context, is not done with any malicious intent, but rather to manifest the near-universal human desire to proclaim, under extraordinary circumstances: “I was here!” The Christian catacombs, in fact, have far older examples of this practice, including very ancient petitions for intercession by local saints (D. Mazzoleni, “Inscriptions in the Roman Catacombs,” *The Christian Catacombs of Rome*, Regensburg, 1999, pp. 180-181). Modern graffiti in the catacombs, however, specifically that left by explorers beginning around the year 1400, tends to be more (self) promotional than devotional, although one could argue that it was also the way to leave an “Ariadne’s thread” through a site. Yet as the charts of J. B. L. G. Seroux D’Agincourt register below (*Viaggio nelle catacombe di Roma*, 1835, pp. 14-15), even the more recent scribbling done in charcoal, pen, lead, and by any other indelible means imaginable over the ancient surfaces of plaster, brick, marble, and clay, has historic value. Antonio Bosio, Giovanni Battista de Rossi, dozens of other catacomb scholars (and some PIAC professors), all left their mark,

Nomi delle Catacombe	Nomi de' privati che le visitarono	Data delle iscrizioni
Pignattara	Lanzoni Filippo 25-01	1703
	Don Diego	1703
S. Calisto	Mangoni	1705
	Giacomo Morelli	1704
Pignattara	Giu. Cimaroni	1709
Crocifisso	P. Raimondo Dielli 19 marzo	1710
	Giuseppe Petrelli	1713
Pignattara	Marangoni	1718
	Boldetti	
	Marangoni 20 gennaio	1730
Crocifisso	P. Giuseppe M. Sio. Capua 22 marzo	1738
	Biagio Resti	1745
Pignattara	Marangoni	1747
Crocifisso	Carigio Memmi Cavatore 7 marzo	1784
	Gio. Giacomo Machiavelli (il costante e laborioso disegnatore ed incisore di quasi tutta la mia opera dal 1780 al 1808	1786
Crocifisso		
Crocifisso	D'Agincourt per la terza ed ultima volta al disotto del nome di Bosio	1786

Notizia de' nomi trovati iscritti nelle Catacombe in occasione de' viaggi che io vi feci nel 1780, 1781, 1783, 1786.

Nomi delle Catacombe	Nomi dei privati che le visitarono	Data delle iscrizioni
	Nicolaus Cochemensis	1511
	Panvini	1595
S. Calisto	Rubens	1591
	Henricus Corvinius del Pheis pharmacopus	1594
	Gioacchino Cilli. Die 29 augusti	1595
	P. Vincenzus Rizony, Siculus	1595
Crocifisso	Antonius Bosius. Die 15 augusti	1598
	Justus Raphelengius	1598
	Gillem Seis	1599
	Melchior Van-Kerbach	1601
S. Calisto	Gio. Anselme d'Anvers	1601
	Zanti Avauzino con Ottavio Pico	1631
	Bosuik	1632
S. Elena con Pignattara	Angelo Contini	1632
	Lorenzo Alamani	1634
Crocifisso	Antonius Bosius, Ottavio Pico post Bosium	1634
	Cesare Fantesi	1670
Crocifisso	Da Carpegna Giov. Cilli cavatore	1692
S. Calisto	Francesco	1692
	For Pignattara	
	Francisco Petrus Paf. Burga	1695
Crocifisso	Francesco de Capito	1697
	Marco	1697

quite literally, on these sites (for the record, I did not). The graffiti testifying to the catacomb visits of Pomponius Laetus and other members of the Accademia Romana degli Antiquari provide unique insight into the operations of that society in fifteenth-century Rome (V. Fiocchi Nicolai, "Origin and Development of Roman Catacombs" in *The Christian Catacombs of Rome*, Regensburg, 1999, p. 10). Graffiti also proves that many 19th and 20th century catacomb "discoveries" were actually made years before. Names now obscure continue to make an impression because their "John Hancock" are in close proximity to well-known crypts and tombs. The tradition continues even today in places like the "graffiti wall" in the crypt opposite the "Madonna and Child" image in the Priscilla catacombs (what scholars of the future will think of our custom of bringing herds of teenagers to ancient tombs will no doubt be largely gathered from this site). Yet the on-going restoration of catacomb paintings does not always appear to conserve modern graffiti-vandalism, although examples of this are no doubt carefully documented and recorded before removal. For this reason, those in the Vigna Randanini catacombs are worth considering before they, too, might disappear.

The Vigna Randanini catacombs have been repeatedly violated and plundered over time, but by forces largely unknown until the site's "official" discovery in 1859. Following the major excavation campaigns of 1859-1864, many tourists flocked to the site, but found it often closed as a result of an 1870 lawsuit filed against the owner, Giuseppe Randanini, for having sold a number of Jewish artifacts to an English gentleman scholar, Charles Willes Wilshere, that are now on display in Oxford's Ashmolean Museum (M. Vickers, "The Wilshere Collection of Early Christian and Jewish Antiquities in the Ashmolean Museum, Oxford," *Miscellanea Emilio Marin sexagenario dicata*, Kacic, 41-43 (2009-2011), pp. 605-614: http://www.franjevci-split.hr/pdf/35_vickers.pdf). After several more decades of casual access to the catacomb, during which time scholars including Orazio Marucchi, Abraham Berlin, and Nikolaus Muller all freely explored the site, the Randanini family was forced to sell off its properties at a bankruptcy auction in 1895, the date, in fact, of what may be the catacomb's earliest modern *graffito*. Since the early 20th century, the property has been in the hands of its current owners, the Marquis del Gallo di Roccagiovine, and the catacomb is one of several buildings and grounds operations the family either maintains or leases out, the others being the restaurant known since 1966 as the "Cecilia Metella" (<http://www.ceciliametella.it/>) and the "Vigna San Sebastiano" function hall (<http://www.vignasansebastiano.eu>). These above-ground commercial ventures are chiefly responsible for the graffiti in the site, given that the majority of examples

date to the first three decades of the 20th century, the time when the restaurant was offering clients special trips to the “wine cellar” (the catacomb), including a visit to the painted cubicula where nearly all the graffiti is now found (Letter of F. S. Manor to *Commentary Magazine*, January, 1978, <http://www.commentarymagazine.com/article/more-on-the-catacombs/>).

The del Gallo di Roccagiovine also continued the practice of arranging private tours, or delegating this task to a caretaker of the site. Foreign guidebooks, most notably the Baedeker and Murray guides, made explicit mention of the catacomb’s location, implying that it was possible to simply drop by, as Italian novelist Giuseppe Cafiero imagines James Joyce doing one afternoon (G. Cafiero, *James Joyce, Roma, ed altre storie*. Bologna, 2006, pp. 241-248). Visits in this manner continued well into the 1930’s, but ceased after the start of World War II. In wartime, the catacomb became a bomb shelter, and a number of artifacts went missing or were destroyed (S. Cappelletti, *The Jewish Community in Rome from the Second Century BCE to the Third Century CE*, Leiden, 2006, p. 152).

At the war’s end, the Randanini site’s official guardian, the Pontifical Commission for Sacred Archaeology, began to monitor access to the Randanini site more carefully. This organization was responsible for much of the restoration and maintenance of the site until 1986, after which point it was turned over to the local Archaeological Superintendence in collaboration with Rome’s Jewish Community. There is a sharp drop-off in graffiti in the catacombs at this time, except for one episode in the early 1970’s when anti-Semitic comments in pencil on the plaster of the cubiculum duplex had to be removed: (PCAS *Giornale di Scavo* 12, 1972).

Current policy in agreement with the Superintendence is to allow limited numbers of visitors into the site in the company of a custodian or qualified guide, all certainly opposed in principle to further property defacement. Resisting the onslaught of mass tourism that has plagued the neighboring catacombs of San Callisto, those in the Vigna Randanini primarily attract archaeology enthusiasts like Andrea, as well as members of the Jewish diaspora the world over, who have always sought out this place for a special type of cultural pilgrimage while in Rome.

The following is a very partial list of signatures on the walls of the painted cubiculum duplex (those in the Palm-Tree cubiculum will be far more challenging to decipher). While incomplete, its data support many of the points raised above about access to the Vigna Randanini catacombs in the late 19th and early 20th centuries. Interestingly enough, it will be seen that American Jewish names top the list. No particular name stands out for historical significance, but that might change with a serious study of this unique characteristic of the site.

1. Gallo Ermanno 1916 16/11/tornato qui 10/13/1944
2. Frasca [star] Gaetano 1932
3. Anno IV/10-7-1927 (Fascist date)
4. Rose/ Samuels/Boston MA
5. Allen/ Goldstein/B Jan 13 1931 (near peacock at entrance)
6. Sara + Arthur Goldman/Bklyn NY 1931
7. Eric Lipson
8. Ruben Goldberg (in Hebrew)/American Sailor/April 6 1919
9. EP EARLSON (or Ericson?)/JEW/CRAM
10. C. P. Assovsky/Milwaukee USA/March 31 1925/with/J. A. Colton of/Fall River, MA.
11. Wanda Moise 21- 1- 34/XII
12. H. Pinkert/3-10-1929
13. Goldstein/Baltimore/Maryland/ USA
14. Eugenio/Sobijk/Polska/1934
15. Abolasch Solomon/Sofia 1927
16. 'Za Stanza/ Principi/Domenico/1902/ Principi/Giuseppe
17. Ferdinando/Cernauti 1939
18. Lenghingin (?) Domenico/16-19-1929
19. Gallo, Giuseppe(e) (connection to Ermanno Gallo, above, or the del Gallo family?)
20. Bergetti, Ferruccio
21. Savio/1951
22. 1896
23. M. Held Romania
24. B. Friedman USA (on the archway over the door!)

